

Metacucujus sp.
Cycad cucujid beetle

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Insect

Size: 3 mm in length

Distribution:

Eastern Cape, north of Kariega

Importance:

This beetle lineage is involved in the pollination of endangered cycads, and the resulting sequence data will inform taxonomic resolution and support our work on host specificity and the recovery of pollinator mutualisms.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 10.45 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 2.23 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.27 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.4% [Single: 94.4%, Duplicated: 5.0%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 1112.84 kilobases

Contig number: 3170

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